

Organic Compounds of Silicon. Part II. Reactions of Chloro- and Alkoxy-silanes with Salicylic Acid and other Hydroxylic and Carboxylic Compounds

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Several derivatives of silicon have been prepared by the reactions of various alkyl and phenyl chloro-silanes and alkoxy-silanes in benzene with salicylic acid. A few reactions have been tried with some aromatic hydroxylic and carboxylic compounds.

The physico-chemical studies of the reaction between the α -hydroxycarboxylic acids and metal ions in aqueous solution have revealed that the hydrogen of the hydroxyl group becomes reactive as a result of chelation and the complex ion dissociates as an acid¹⁻³.

In view of the above, a systematic study of the reaction of various silanes (both chloro and alkoxy) with salicylic acid was made. Similar reactions between alkoxides of germanium⁴, titanium⁵, and zirconium⁶ with salicylic acid in benzene resulted in ready replacement of the alkoxy groups by the carboxylate group at low temperatures and it was shown that the phenoxy hydrogen also became reactive at higher temperatures. For example, the reaction of zirconium isopropylate with salicylic acid⁶ (molar ratio 1:2) can be represented as :

Reactions of anhydrous chlorides of the above elements with salicylic acid have also been studied in detail with similar results.

In the present investigation the reactions of salicylic acid with silicon tetrachloride, dichlorodimethylsilane, dichlorodiphenylsilane, chlorotrimethylsilane, tetraethoxysilane, and diethoxydimethylsilane have been studied in benzene medium. In case of chloro compounds, the reaction mixture was refluxed in the solvent till the evolution of hydrogen chloride gas had almost ceased, whereas in case of ethoxy compounds, the liberated ethanol was removed azeotropically with benzene and estimated.

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Replacement of chlorine atoms is very rapid in the case of silicon tetrachloride and other alkyl and phenyl chlorosilanes. Replacement of the ethoxy groups in diethoxydimethylsilane also proceeds quite rapidly. In case of tetraethoxysilane, the first two ethoxy groups are replaced quite rapidly, but the replacement of the third proceeds slowly on refluxing. The reactions between alkoxy silanes and salicylic acid were also attempted in cold, but with negative results. Analyses of the products indicate that various reactions may be represented as:

Of the above, compounds (I), (II), and (III) are colorless liquids, miscible with benzene; compound (VI) is a chocolate, viscous liquid, soluble in benzene and compounds (IV), (V), and (VII) are solids, insoluble in hydrocarbons. Compounds (I) and (II) have been distilled under reduced pressure, whereas (III) and (VI) decompose on being heated under reduced pressure.

The above ready replaceability of the alkoxy groups of tetraethoxysilane and diethoxydimethylsilane with salicylic acid is in sharp contrast with the comparatively low reactivity of such compounds⁷ with alcohols, phenols, carboxylic acids, and other hydroxy-carboxylic compounds. Alkoxides of germanium⁸, titanium⁹⁻¹¹, and zirconium¹² react readily with all the above groups of compounds. Compared to the above, reports about the reactivity of even tetraethoxysilane with higher alcohols and phenols are at variance with each other¹³⁻¹⁵. In view of the above, the reactions of tetraethoxysilane and diethoxydimethylsilane with phenol and benzoic acid were also attempted. Even when the reactions were carried out in benzene medium under an efficient fractionating column to remove the ethanol produced azeotropically, there was no noticeable replacement at all. The non-reactivity of phenol and benzoic acid individually with ethoxysilanes is in sharp contrast to the observed facile reaction with salicylic acid. One possible explanation is that the chelation effect present in derivatives of the above type may be responsible for the greater reactivity of salicylic acid. To test this, the reactions of tetraethoxysilane and diethoxydimethylsilane with catechol and phthalic acid were also attempted, but these also did not show any reaction, indicating that mere chelation had no effect on the reactivities of the above types of compounds. An interesting observation of the ready replaceability of both the ethoxy groups of diethoxydimethylsilane by *p*-chlorophenol¹⁶ has been confirmed and it appears that suitable inductive effect might be more responsible for the above differences. Further work is in progress with a number of substituted phenols as well as α -hydroxycarboxylic acids to elucidate the point further.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethanol liberated in the azeotrope was estimated by oxidation with $N\text{-K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ (in 12.5% H_2SO_4)¹⁷. Salicylate was estimated by alkaline permanganate oxidation¹⁸. In the case of alkyl derivatives, silicon was estimated by digestion with a mixture of H_2SO_4 (conc.), solid ammonium sulphate, and solid ammonium nitrate¹⁹. In all the other compounds, estimation was done in a platinum crucible by ignition to silica.

Reactions of Methyl- and Phenyl-chlorosilanes with Salicylic Acid

(1) Salicylic acid (2.76 g.) was refluxed with dichlorodimethylsilane (2.58 g.) in benzene (50 ml). At a bath temperature of about 80°, whole of the acid passed into solution with a

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yellow colour. The reaction mixture was refluxed at a bath temperature of 100-115° till the evolution of HCl fumes had ceased (20 hours). Excess benzene was distilled and the product dried at ordinary temperature and 0.1 mm pressure for 4 hours when a light yellow liquid was obtained; b.p. 114°/1.5 mm, yield 81%. (Found: Si, 14.9; salicylate, 69.18. $C_9H_{10}O_3Si$ requires Si, 14.4; salicylate, 70.1%).

(2). Salicylic acid (8.28 g.) was refluxed with chlorotrimethylsilane (6.54 g.) and benzene (50 ml) at a bath temperature of 80-95° till the evolution of HCl gas had ceased (58 hours). Excess benzene was distilled and the product dried at ordinary temperature and 0.8 mm pressure for 5 hours. A purple-coloured liquid was obtained which became colorless on distillation; b.p. 105°-107°/1.5 mm; yield 95%. (Found: Si, 13.29; salicylate, 64.8. $C_{10}H_{14}O_3Si$ requires Si, 13.33; salicylate, 65.2%).

(3). Salicylic acid (4.099 g.) was refluxed with dichlorodiphenylsilane (7.5 g.) and benzene (50 ml) till the evolution of HCl gas had ceased (80 hours). Excess benzene was distilled and the product dried at ordinary temperature and 0.95 mm pressure for 5 hours. A viscous product was obtained (97%). When it was heated under reduced pressure (0.1 mm) it decomposed, affording a white solid containing no silicon; it was found to be salicylic acid (it developed violet colour with ferric chloride). (Found: Si, 8.67; salicylate, 42.3. $C_9H_4O_3Si$ requires Si, 8.8; salicylate, 42.76%).

(4). Reaction between silicon tetrachloride and salicylic acid was tried in the molar ratios of 1:1 and 1:2. In both cases, the same product was obtained (*vide infra*).

(a) Silicon tetrachloride (3.7 g.) was distilled directly to the reaction flask. To it was added benzene (30 ml). Salicylic acid (3.0 g.) was added with the help of benzene. Vigorous reaction occurred even in cold with brisk evolution of HCl gas and precipitation of a creamish yellow powder. The reaction mixture was refluxed at a bath temperature of 110° for 2 hours to expel HCl gas produced. While distilling excess benzene, a fraction was obtained at 58-59° which was found to be silicon tetrachloride. The solid powder was dried at room temperature at 0.1 mm pressure for 2 hours and then at a bath temperature of 40° and 0.1 mm pressure for a further period of 2 hours. Thus a very light powder was obtained. It was found to be insoluble in benzene and CCl_4 and soluble to some extent in ether; yield 99.85%. (Found: Si, 9.80; salicylate, 90.14. $C_4H_8O_6Si$ requires Si, 9.3; salicylate, 90.60%).

Higher percentage of silicon is probably due to the hydrolysis of some of the silicon tetrachloride present in excess.

(b) Salicylic acid (2.76 g.) was added to silicon tetrachloride (1.70 g.) with the help of benzene (50 ml). The mixture was shaken thoroughly after attaching the flask to a reflux condenser. The flask was then immersed in an oil bath and heated. At a bath temperature of 70°, HCl gas started coming at the top of the condenser and after about 15 mins., white turbidity appeared in the benzene layer, and finally a white precipitate settled down. The whole was refluxed for about 4 hours to expel HCl gas. Excess benzene was distilled and the compound dried at 40°/0.1 mm for 3 hours when a creamish yellow powder was obtained; yield 99.95%. (Found: Si, 9.36; salicylate, 90.29. $C_4H_8O_6Si$ requires Si, 9.30; salicylate, 90.60%).

(c) The above compound (0.98 g.) was dissolved in dry ethanol (10 ml) and refluxed at a bath temperature of 100°-10°. The alcohol was removed over the pump and the resulting white product was dried at room temperature and 0.1 mm pressure for 3 hours. (Found: Si, 8.03; salicylate, 78.09. $C_{16}H_{14}O_7Si$ requires Si, 8.03; salicylate, 78.60%.)

Reactions of Tetraethoxysilane with Salicylic Acid

In Molar Ratio of 1:1.—Salicylic acid (2.77 g.) was added to tetraethoxysilane (4.24 g.) with the help of benzene (60 ml). On shaking a light yellow colour developed. The mixture was refluxed at a bath temperature of 110-15° over a fractionating column for 3 hours. Bath temperature was then raised to 140° when ethanol-benzene azeotrope started distilling at the top at 68°. Temperature remained constant at 68° for about 45 mins., then at 72° for about 1 hour, and finally reached 80°. It was refluxed again for 45 mins. and the distillate collected again. In the reaction flask a yellow solution was obtained. It was dried over the pump at 40°/0.01 mm for 3 hours when a chocolate-coloured, viscous liquid was obtained. Azeotrope: Calc. for 2 moles of ethanol, 1.83 g. Ethanol found: 1.754 g. (Found: Si, 10.98; salicylate, 52.94. $C_{11}H_{14}O_3Si$ requires Si, 11.2; salicylate, 53.3%.)

In Molar Ratio of 1:2.—Salicylic acid (1.47 g.) was added with the help of benzene (60 ml) to tetraethoxysilane (1.1286 g.) and the whole was shaken. No reaction occurred in the cold. The reaction mixture was refluxed at a bath temperature of 105-10° over a fractionating column for 5 hours. A yellow solution was obtained. Bath temperature was raised to 140° when ethanol-benzene azeotrope started distilling at the top at 68° and a solid began to separate. Analysis of the azeotrope showed the liberation of 2.3 moles of ethanol only. The whole was again refluxed at 110-15° for next 5 hours and the azeotrope was collected again. A white solid remained in the flask. It was dried at 40°/0.1 mm for 3 hours; yield 96%. Azeotrope: Calc. for 3 moles of ethanol, 0.73 g. Ethanol found: 0.66 g. (Found: Si, 8.3; salicylate, 77.9. $C_{16}H_{14}O_7Si$ requires Si, 8.03; salicylate, 78.60%.)

Reaction of Diethoxydimethylsilane with Salicylic Acid

Salicylic acid (1.38 g.) was added with the help of benzene (60 ml) to diethoxydimethylsilane (1.48 g.). The mixture was refluxed at a bath temperature of 110-15° for 3 hours over a fractionating column. The temperature was raised to 138° when ethanol-benzene azeotrope started distilling at the top at 68°. It was collected. Excess benzene was distilled and the compound dried at room temperature (0.1 mm) for 3 hours; b.p. 114°/1.5 mm; yield 95%. Azeotrope: Calc. for 2 moles of ethanol, 0.9 g. Ethanol found: 0.889 g. (Found: Si, 14.32; salicylate, 69.4. $C_9H_{10}O_3Si$ requires Si, 14.4; salicylate, 70.1%.)

Reaction of Diethoxydimethylsilane with p-Chlorophenol

A mixture of diethoxydimethylsilane (1.48 g.), p-chlorophenol (2.58 g.), and benzene (60 ml) was refluxed for 4 hours under a fractionating column. The ethanol-benzene azeotrope was collected at 68°. Residual liquid was dried at 50°/0.1 mm for 2 hours; b.p. 188°/0.8 mm, yield 91%. Azeotrope: Calc. for 2 moles of ethanol, 0.9 g. Ethanol found: 0.887. (Found: Si, 8.32. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{14}O_2Cl_2Si$: Si, 9.0%.)

Reactions between Diethoxydimethylsilane and Benzoic Acid

In Molar Ratio of 1:2.—The mixture containing benzoic acid (2.44 g.), diethoxydimethylsilane (2.96 g.), and benzene (50 ml) was refluxed for 4 hours under a fractionating column. No ethanol was detected in the distillate. Residue in the flask was dried under vacuum whereby a white solid (2.41 g.), found to be benzoic acid, was obtained, showing that no reaction had occurred.

In Molar Ratio of 1:2.—The above reaction, studied by mixing the two components in 1:2 ratio, showed a negative result.

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